

SUPERSATURATION LIMITS OF SOLUTIONS. PART I

BY RAMA GOPAL

It is shown that aqueous solutions of some salts, saturated at temperature T_s , when cooled uniformly in a thin-walled sealed glass tube, crystallise at almost a fixed temperature T . Further, $T_s - T$ is found to be approximately constant for the same solute irrespective of the value of T_s within the temperature range studied herein. Again for some of the salts investigated the molecular heat of solution, λ appears to vary inversely as $T_s - T$, i.e., $(T_s - T)\lambda = \text{a constant (approx.)}$. A theoretical deduction of this relationship, based on the theory of supersaturation of Jones and Partington has been advanced.

In some cases, $T_s - T$ has, however, been found to increase rapidly with successive heating and cooling. The difference between the behaviours of these two types of salts is noted without suggesting any hypothesis to explain this difference.

A third type of substances has been observed to show no spontaneous crystallisation even after considerable cooling. Behaviours of the first and the third type of substances have been discussed.

A survey of literature reveals that no serious attempt has been made to study the relative supersaturation of various substances in any given solvent and its dependence on any property of the entities concerned. Jones (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 1739) pointed out that relative supersaturation of KNO_3 , RbNO_3 and CsNO_3 varied inversely as their molecular weight, and probably, directly as their hydration. Jones and Partington (*Phil. Mag.*, 1915, 29, 35; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915 197, 1019) emphasised the importance of the surface energy of the solute in the phenomenon of supersaturation. But apart from a few more investigations of more or less qualitative nature no other significant work is available. It is, therefore, desirable to study various substances from the point of view of their relative supersaturation in the commonest solvent water to start with.

From the researches of Berkley (*Phil. Mag.*, 1912, 24, 254), Young and his collaborators (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 33, 148, 1375; 1913, 35, 1065) and others it appears that spontaneous crystallisation in a solution or melt is to a very great extent dependent on the mechanical shock to which it is subjected as well as on the number and nature of the insoluble nuclei present. It is, therefore, essential that all experiments must be performed under comparable conditions to get the relative values of supersaturation. Also from these works it is definitely established that the *metastable range*, in Ostwald's terminology, may not be a very suitable expression to denote the region of relative supersaturation as solutions in this region have been supposed to be quite immune to crystallisation under all circumstances except the addition of nuclei from without. For this reason it is preferably called here *the supersaturation limit* to denote the difference between the saturation temperature T_s and that of spontaneous crystallisation T (both in degrees centigrade) when a solution in a thin-walled sealed glass tube cools uniformly at rest.

EXPERIMENTAL

Required amounts of water and chemicals (necessary for saturation at any temperature T_s) recrystallised from conductivity water and protected from dust as far as possible, were sealed in well steamed and dried similar thin-walled glass tubes. Generally 4 g. of water were used. The sealed tube was attached to a stout glass tubing with rubber bands and placed in a beaker (800 to 1000 c.c. capacity) containing water enough to keep it wholly immersed. The beaker was heated to a temperature approximately 10° higher than T_s of the solution in the tube. By repeated

shakings the solute was dissolved in the minimum possible time. The beaker was then allowed to cool slowly, keeping the sealed tube completely at rest, the temperature of the beaker falling by 1° in about 5 to 10 minutes. It was arranged with the help of a microburner placed under the beaker. This device assures that the temperature inside the sealed tube is the same as that of the outer bath. Some control experiments with similar tubes carrying 4 g. of water, and a thermometer dipped in it, and closed at the mouth with a cork, were performed in the above bath which cooled unaided by a microburner. It has been found that when temperature falls 1° in about 5 minutes, the temperatures inside the closed tube and outside in the beaker are the same.

The temperature T of the bath, at which spontaneous crystallisation in the sealed tube started was noted. Observations were made with the help of a pocket lens. The above process of heating and cooling was repeated three times or more and observations made as before. Thermometers used were graduated in $1/5^\circ$ and were standardised against a thermometer with National Physical Laboratory certificate. Solubilities used were as recent as possible. Graphs were plotted from available figures in case where solubilities were not given at proper interval of temperatures and from these graphs required solubilities were read off. But older values from Comey and Hahn's "Dictionary of Chemical Solubilities etc," were employed where recent works failed to show any marked difference. The results thus obtained are given in the following tables.

In a number of other aqueous solutions like those of SnCl_2 , HIO_3 , ZnCl_2 , CH_3COONa , CdSO_4 , $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ etc. it has not been possible to get any temperature of spontaneous crystallisation within the range of temperatures investigated.

From the tables it is clear that in some cases the temperature T remains almost constant after repeated heatings and coolings whereas in others it varies with the number of heatings. $T_1 - T$, in general, is obtained with the first temperature of spontaneous crystallisation as in this

TABLE I

T_1	KCl				$T_1 - T$	T_1	KBr				$T_1 - T$	T_1	KI				$T_1 - T$
	T	T	T	T			T	T	T	T			T	T	T	T	
40	21'0	21'0	21'6	19'0	37	20'0	20'2	20'0	17'0	35	20'0	20'2	20'0	15'0			
45	26'0	26'5	25'8	19'0	42	25'2	25'0	25'4	16'8	40	24'6	25'0	23'6	15'4			
50	30'4	30'2	30'0	19'6	45	28'6	28'5	28'0	16'4	45	29'4	29'8	29'6	15'6			
55	38'6	38'5	37'4	16'4	50	34'0	34'5	33'8	16'0	50	34'2	35'0	34'4	15'8			
60	42'8	42'0	40'4	17'2	55	38'4	38'5	38'0	16'0	55	45'0	39'6	39'4	15'4			
65	45'8	46'0	45'6	19'2	58	41'4	40'6	42'2	16'6	60	44'8	44'2	44'2	15'2			
70	49'6	47'4	43'0	20'4	65	49'2	48'8	48'4	15'8	65	49'6	50'2	49'5	15'4			
75	54'4	48'4	54'0	20'6	70	52'8	53'4	52'8	17'2	70	54'6	—	—	15'4			
80	59'8	59'6	52'8	20'2	75	55'8	57'4	58'8	16'2	77	61'8	62'6	61'6	15'2			
				Mean 19'5	80	62'6	62'6	62'4	17'4	80	64'6	64'2	64'0	15'4			
								Mean 16'3					Mean 15'5				

TABLE I (contd.)

KClO ₃					KClO ₄					KBrO ₃				
T ₂	T.		T ₂ -T.	T ₁	T ₂	T.		T ₂ -T.	T ₁	T ₂	T.		T ₂ -T.	
30	24.0	23.6	23.0	6.0	30	23.6	24.0	23.5	6.4	35	26.0	25.4	21.0	9.0
37	30.6	30.5	30.0	6.4	33	27.0	27.2	27.5	6.0	40	31.5	31.0	31.0, 30.0	8.5
40	33.4	33.5	32.0	6.6	35	28.4	28.0	27.6	6.6	45	36.0	35.4	34.6	9.0
45	39.0	39.0	38.4	6.0	40	33.8	33.5	33.5	6.2	48	39.0	36.4	37.2	9.0
50	43.4	43.5	43.0	6.6	45	39.0	38.9	38.8	6.0	50	40.6	40.0	38.2	9.4
55	47.8	47.4	47.2	7.2	50	43.5	43.7	43.7	6.5	55	46.8	46.2	39.2	8.2
60	53.4	53.0	53.6	6.6	52.5	46.8	47.0	46.0	5.7	60	51.0	51.2	50.6	9.0
62.5	56.0	55.8	52.6	6.5	55	48.6	48.0	48.4	6.4	68	60.6	60.5	59.6	7.4
65	57.4	56.6	56.6	7.6	60	53.4	53.4	53.4	6.6	70	61.6	61.6	62.0	8.4
70	63.0	63.6	62.9	7.0	65	58.1	57.6	57.4	6.7	75	65.8	65.2	63.8	9.2
			Mean	6.6				Mean	6.3				Mean	8.8

KNO ₃					KIO ₃					NaNO ₃				
T ₂	T.		T ₂ -T.	T ₁	T ₂	T.		T ₂ -T.	T ₁	T ₂	T.		T ₂ -T.	
35	22.8	21.5	21.5	12.2	35	—	24.0	—	—	40	26.0	26.5	26.2	14.0
40	25.8	25.5	26.0	14.2	40	29.0	27.0	—	11.0	43	29.0	28.6	28.0	14.0
45	31.5	32.0	31.7	13.5	45	30.6	27.0	—	14.5	45	32.0	32.4	32.0	13.0
50	37.0	37.0	36.2	13.0	50	35.8	33.4	30.0	14.2	50	38.0	38.2	40.0	12.0
55	42.0	42.0	41.2	13.0	55	40.6	38.6	37.6	14.4	55	42.1	41.4	41.4	12.9
60	46.6	46.4	46.8	13.4	60	47.2	47.0	43.4	12.8	58	45.2	45.1	45.4	12.8
65	52.6	52.2	52.4	12.4	65	51.0	47.2	42.6	14.0	60	47.2	47.0	46.8	12.8
70	56.6	56.8	56.6	13.4	70	55.9	52.2	52.0	14.1	65	51.2	51.6	51.2	13.8
75	62.6	62.6	62.6	12.4	75	61.6	60.6	56.5	13.4	70	57.6	57.9	58.0	12.4
80	66.9	66.6	66.8	13.2	80	67.0	67.0	65.6	13.0	75	61.4	61.2	61.6	13.6
			Mean	13.0				Mean	13.5				Mean	13.0

* Solutions did not crystallise down to these temperatures.

TABLE II

Substance	T ₂	T.		T ₂ -T.	Substance	T ₂	T.		T ₂ -T.						
Ba(NO ₃) ₂	50	32.0	28.2	26.2	18.0	Oxalic acid	50	35.0	30.2	31.4	28.2	15.0			
	55	36.4	33.2	25.4	18.6		55	40.8	36.0	33.2	34.0	—	14.2		
	60	41.2	37.0	28.4	18.8		60	47.2	47.4	40.1	35.0	35.2	12.2		
	65	46.2	47.4	37.0	18.8		65	51.0	48.3	45.6	44.2	45.0	14.0		
	70	51.4	44.2	31.8	18.6		70	57.4	47.2	42.2	47.3	57.0	12.5		
	75	57.5	56.8	46.2	42.0		17.5								
NH ₄ Cl	55	35.0	28.2	24.4	26.0	21.5	20.0	Urea	82	68.6	60.5	60.6	49.4	68.6	11.4
	60	38.2	30.0	35.1	31.1	26.0	21.8		70	57.4	57.8	45.2	44.0	38.2	12.6
	65	52.4	42.2	28.0	27.2	28.0	12.6		60	47.0	45.2	46.9	47.0	41.0	13.0
									50	35.6	25.0	—	—	—	14.4
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	55	34.0	29.6	26.4	25.0	21.0	Succinic acid	45	32.0	30.0	25.6	23.0	—	13.0	
	60	36.5	34.0	25.4	24.2	23.5		55	35.4	32.0	28.2	—	—	19.6	
	65	41.2	39.4	30.2	29.6	23.8		60	45.4	43.6	38.2	40.0	42.0	15.6	
	70	45.2	40.0	31.0	30.8	24.8		65	44.3	42.5	39.0	—	—	20.8	
	80	55.4	50.2	35.0	34.5	24.6		70	49.4	47.3	48.4	47.0	41.2	20.6	
							74	53.4	54.6	55.6	45.2	—	19.6		
							80	59.0	58.0	55.0	50.8	54.0	21.0		

condition all the solutions may be expected to be in identical environments. It must not be assumed, however, that solutions would not crystallise above T under any circumstances. Effects of mechanical stimulus and insoluble nuclei are well known (*loc. cit.*). Prolonged keeping above T may bring about crystallisation as is clear from the researches of Jaffe (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1903, 43, 565) and others. What is implied by T is that this temperature appears to lie in the most favourable position on the temperature-energy diagrams obtained by Young (*loc. cit.*). The energy value corresponds to that of the shocks prevalent in a common laboratory room, *i.e.*, at this temperature the solution crystallises out under the influence of shocks prevalent in laboratory rooms within the time of experiments.

DISCUSSION

Referring to monobasic salts of Na and K given above it appears that the molecular heat of solution λ of the salts varies almost inversely as the corresponding $T_s - T$, *i.e.*, $\lambda(T_s - T)$ is approximately constant. This is clear from Table II.

The constancy of the expression $(T_s - T)\lambda$ follows from the equation of Jones and Partington (*loc. cit.*). This equation connects the absolute temperature T and the radius r of the solute particle which is in equilibrium with a solution saturated at T (*i.e.* particles of smaller radii will dissolve but of greater ones will start spontaneous crystallisation at this temperature) in the relationship,

$$T = C(1 - 1/k\tau) \quad \dots (i)$$

where C is the integration constant and $k = \rho\lambda/2M\sigma$, the terms used have their usual significance. The equation (i) is applicable to solutions of substances with negative heat of solution and only the numerical values of λ should be taken into account as the general expression $T = C\left(1 + \frac{1}{k\tau}\right)$ reduces to (i) when proper value of λ is substituted. When T equals the ordinary saturation temperature T_s , $\tau = \infty$. In this case $T_s = C$ (ii)

$$\text{From (i) and (ii) we obtain} \quad (T_s - T) = \frac{C}{k\tau} = T_s \frac{\rho\lambda r}{2M\sigma} = \frac{2\sigma M}{\rho\lambda} \cdot \frac{T_s}{r}$$

$$\text{or} \quad \lambda(T_s - T) = \frac{2\sigma M}{\rho} \cdot \frac{T_s}{r} = 2\sigma V_m \cdot \frac{T_s}{r} \quad \dots (iii)$$

where V_m denotes the molecular volume. According to various workers (Jones and Partington, *loc. cit.*, de Coppet and Tammann, "Krystallisieren und Schmelzen," Leipzig, 1903, p. 148)

TABLE III

Salt.	$-\lambda$.	$(T_s - T)$.	$-\lambda(T_s - T)^*$.	Salt.	$-\lambda$.	$(T_s - T)$.	$-M(T_s - T)^*$.	
KCl	4246	19.5	78897	KClO ₃	9950	6.6	65670	
KBr	5080	16.3	82804	KNO ₃ †	8800	13.0	114400	
KI	5110	15.5	79205	KClO ₄	12200	6.3	76230	
KBrO ₃	9760	8.8	84788	NaNO ₃	5030	13.0	65390	
KIO ₃	6780	13.5	91490	NaCl‡	1220	51.0	62220	
							Mean	8000 (approx.)

* As the values of λ given here correspond to very dilute solutions, the relationship must be considered as highly approximate.

† An average value derived from the observations of Jaffe (*loc. cit.*) is 13.8 as Table IV shows.

‡ It was difficult to observe the formation of crystals in this case due to an almost colourless nature of crystals and their slow growth. But it was observed $T_s - T$ to be about 50. This is, however, in close agreement with the value obtained by de Coppet (*Compt. rend.*, 1872, 75, 328) according to whom it is about 47 to 51.

TABLE IV

KNO ₃ (in 100 g. of water).	T _s .	T.	(T _s -T).	KNO ₃ (in 100 g. of water).	T _s .	T.	(T _s -T)
45.0 g.	30.5	17.5	13.0	58.6 g.	37.3	22.8	14.5
51.8	33.8	19.4	14.4	62.9	39.4	26.2	13.5
53.4	34.8	20.0	14.2				
						Mean	13.8

τ varies as T_s , i.e., T_s/τ is a constant. Further τ in the case of similar substances may be taken to be of the same order. So that

$$\lambda(T_s - T)\lambda_s \propto \sigma V_m$$

The researches of Jaeger* (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1917, 101, 185) and Dundon (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 2665) show that σV_m is approximately constant for similar substances. Assuming that σV_m does not change much within the range of temperatures studied, it follows that

$$(T_s - T)\lambda = \text{a constant (approx.)}$$

From the results arrived at above electrolytes can be roughly divided into three main classes. First types are those in which supersaturation is, in general, not very great and almost a constant $T_s - T$ is obtained at least in the first few heatings, e.g., KNO₃, KClO₄, etc., or the variation in $T_s - T$ with number of heatings is small. Second type comprises those for which $T_s - T$ increases rapidly with repeated heatings, e.g., Ba(NO₃)₂, NH₄Cl, etc. Jaffe (*loc. cit.*) has shown that $T_s - T$ can be increased even in the case of KNO₃ by intensive filtration of the solution although it may be seen from the observations that it does not appreciably change up to 5 to 6 operations in most cases. Similarly Issac (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 384) pointed out that in solutions of $x\text{NaNO}_3 : y\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 : z\text{H}_2\text{O}$ mixtures when boiled from 18 to 30 hours, $T_s - T$ increases even when tubes are shaken while cooling. This is well explained on the assumption of the presence of dust nuclei which are gradually removed in the process of filtration or on continuous boiling. The effect of heating on supersaturation limits has been very exhaustively studied by a number of workers specially in the case of organic liquids and various theories have been put forward depending mainly on the assumption of the presence of crystalline nuclei which are gradually dissolved or broken up into less effective smaller fragments in the process of heating. These have been well summarised by Richards (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 479) and Richards, Kirkpatrick and Hutz (*ibid.*, 1936, 58, 2243). It is very difficult to fit in these theories in the extreme case of the first type of above mentioned substances unless we assume that these are very sensitive to crystalline nuclei while the others are not so. It is premature to make any decision or suggest another hypothesis at the present stage. It is expected that further investigation might lead to some definite conclusion.

To the third category belong the substances which show no spontaneous crystallisation even on strong cooling, e.g., CH₃COONa, Na₂S₂O₈, HIO₃, SnCl₄, AlCl₃, ZnCl₂, etc. (*cf.* Bhattacharya and Dhar, *Proc. Akad. Wetensch.*, 1915, 18, 369; Seysenegg, *Mikrochem.*, 1939, 27, 96). Great affinity of these substances for water molecules is supported by the researches of Jones, Biltz and their collaborators as well as by the recent work on the entropy of ions and their apparent

* Only σ of melts are given. It may be reasonably expected that for similar solutes, i.e., solutes which behave similarly towards the solvent (water) the variations, if at all, will also be similar though they may not be exactly identical.

ionic volumes in aqueous solution. It may be added that most of these substances have got a positive heat of solution in the anhydrous condition.

It may now be visualised how in the case of type III salts a very high supersaturation is obtained. On dissolution a very compact sheath of water molecules is formed round the ions and molecules of the solute as the affinity between them is very high, whereas a very weak binding, if at all, occurs with substances of the first type. Hence the formation of stable nuclei is easier in the case of substances of type I but difficult in those of type III as the lattice forming units will hardly have any chance of coming together during the normal course of time. Moreover, it will be easier for the entities in the former type to smash through weak covering of water molecules around them and join hands with their opposite number when their affinity under these circumstances overcomes the effect of the outer sheath but it will be difficult and highly improbable in the case of substances of type III due to compact nature of the outer coverings. Besides, the high viscosity of the aqueous solutions of these substances, which is most probably due to their great affinity for water molecules, hinders the free movement of the lattice-forming units the probability of whose coming together is, therefore, further reduced. The above two reasons appear to be mainly responsible for their high supersaturation. The effect of stirring, which helps the entities to come together more frequently, supports this view. When stable nuclei are once formed, however, crystallisation starts because the strong surface forces outweigh the effects of the outer sheath and the process continues till the equilibrium is established.

The author wishes to express his thanks to Dr. A. C. Chatterji for guidance and to the Lucknow University for the award of a fellowship which has enabled him to undertake this work.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
THE UNIVERSITY,
LUCKNOW.

Received July 27, 1942.
